

Impact ionization in silicon at low charge-carrier energies

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Photons absorbed in silicon produce electron-hole pairs which can cause impact ionization and quantum yield larger than one. A reliable determination of quantum yield at low charge-carrier energies (<4 eV) has been challenging because photon losses due to reflectance and charge-carrier losses due to recombination affect the resulting photocurrent. We present here how the measurement of this fundamental characteristic of silicon crystal can be improved in the charge-carrier energy range of 1.6 eV – 4 eV by using a Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector (PQED) based on induced junction photodiodes optimized for photon-to-electron conversion efficiency. The measured quantum yield values are compared with the results of theoretical calculations revealing increased impact-ionization probabilities at 2.25 eV and 3.23 eV on top of a smooth background curve calculated by a model based on free charge carriers in the silicon lattice. For the results at the lowest energies, both data and an asymptotic extrapolation model suggest that quantum yield exceeds unity by $\sim 10^{-4}$ at 1.6 eV corresponding to a photon wavelength of 450 nm.

Silicon detectors are widely used for measurement of light and for energy conversion in solar cells. An extensive literature is available on analyzing the detection efficiency including effects of impact ionization.^{1–6} Quantum yield due to impact ionization is also important in scientific applications, such as photon/particle detectors in astronomy^{7–10} and primary standards of spectral responsivity.^{11–14} Understanding impact ionization processes is important for these applications as the measured signal often critically depends on quantum yield. Experimental data on impact ionization can be obtained by injecting hot charge carriers in silicon by tunneling¹⁵ or by photon irradiation^{2,7} and measuring the resulting electrical current. There are limitations on these experiments at low charge-carrier energies, where not much reliable data below 2 eV kinetic energies are available. Photon irradiation experiments^{2,6,16,17} often suffer from large reflectance and charge-carrier recombination losses which affect the measured photocurrent, while the tunneling experiments¹⁵ struggle with the determination of the exposed energy. Thus, also a basic question on the location of any threshold energy of impact ionization above the indirect energy gap $E_g = 1.12$ eV at room temperature remains unanswered.

We introduce here a method that allows reliable impact ionization data in silicon to be obtained for determining quantum yield at low charge-carrier energies. The method is based on a silicon photodiode detector, **which is known as Predictable Quantum Efficient Detector (PQED)**, where the reflectance and charge-carrier recombination losses are made so small that they do not influence the results, or any remaining losses can be corrected with low uncertainty.^{11–14} Data on quantum yield above 1 are obtained between charge-carrier energies of 1.6 eV and 4 eV and compared with the results of theoretical calculations.

The charge-carrier recombination losses are largely eliminated by the use of *p*-type induced junction photodiodes with 5 V reverse biasing. Thick thermally grown SiO₂ layer on top of a very lightly doped silicon substrate $\sim 10^{12} - 10^{13}$ cm⁻³ contains trapped surface charge close to the Si/SiO₂

interface.¹¹ This charge generates an *n*-type inversion layer and produces a depletion region required for photocurrent generation. As there is so little impurity doping in the photodiode, the density of bulk recombination centers is reduced. Furthermore, the surface recombination velocity is also small and the total relative losses by charge-carrier recombination are less than $1.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ at wavelengths above $\lambda = 400$ nm,¹⁴ as shown by the solid purple line in Fig. 1. **Penetration depth in silicon reduces by one order of magnitude from 100 nm at $\lambda = 400$ nm to 10 nm at $\lambda = 360$ nm.**¹⁸ **The relation between the penetration depth and charge-carrier recombination losses between 400 nm and 500 nm¹⁴ has been used for the extrapolation of losses indicated by the dashed purple line in Fig. 1. The extrapolation assumes that the spectral shape of charge-carrier recombination losses is the same as the spectral shape of inverse penetration depth. This assumption is approximately valid between 400 nm and 500 nm. The penetration depth stays constant within a factor of two between 360 nm and 245 nm, which leads to corresponding weak wavelength dependence also in the extrapolated charge-carrier losses in this spectral range.**

In the PQED, two 11 mm \times 22 mm induced junction photodiodes of 220 nm and 300 nm layer thicknesses of SiO₂ are combined as a wedge trap detector,¹¹ where the outgoing light beam is strongly attenuated by several reflections inside the detector (Fig. 2). The reflectance of the PQED can be determined either by calculation according to the geometry and the refractive indices of SiO₂¹⁹ and silicon¹⁸ or by measuring the relative intensity of the outgoing beam. The reflectance **of the trap** is smaller than $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ in the visible wavelength range (Fig. 1). Spectral responsivity of the PQED in the units of A/W is

$$R(h\nu) = \frac{e}{h\nu} (1 - \rho(h\nu))(1 - \delta(h\nu))(1 + g(h\nu)), \quad (1)$$

where $e/(h\nu)$ is the responsivity of an ideal quantum detector expressed by the elementary charge e and the photon energy $h\nu$. Parameters $\rho(h\nu)$ and $\delta(h\nu)$ describe the losses by spec-

FIG. 1: Simulated charge-carrier recombination losses in PQED photodiodes from Ref. 14 (purple curve) and calculated reflectance losses of 7-reflection PQED with p -polarized (blue curve) and s -polarized light (orange curve). The dashed purple curve represents extrapolation (see text for details).

tral reflectance and recombination of charge carriers, respectively, and $1 + g(h\nu)$ is the quantum yield. **Quantum yield may be larger than one and is here defined as the average number of electrons per absorbed photon in the photodiode, caused by impact ionization in silicon.** Equation (1) neglects any losses due to transmission through the photodiode because the light penetration depth in silicon is less than $2 \mu\text{m}$ at the wavelengths used in this work.¹⁸

Our measurement setup consists of a xenon light source, grating monochromator, PQED under test, a broadband wire-grid polarizer for producing light with different polarization states, and a reference pyroelectric radiometer calibrated for measurement of optical power. Photocurrent signal from the PQED was divided by the optical power obtained from the pyroelectric radiometer to determine the measured spectral responsivity $R(h\nu)$ of Eq. (1). To reduce noise in the data, measurements were repeated several times and then averaged. Results with p - and s -polarized incident light are displayed in Fig. 3.²⁰ The relative expanded uncertainty of these data is 1%.

Impact ionization causes the measured spectral responsivity in Fig. 3 to deviate at the ultraviolet region from the ideal responsivity of quantum detector indicated by the solid line. The responsivity for s -polarized light is lower than for p -polarized light at wavelengths 250 nm to 310 nm, because reflectance of the former is larger in that spectral range as seen in Fig. 1. Also, it is seen that the reflectance is larger than the recombination losses. With known values of $e/(h\nu)$, $\rho(h\nu)$ and $\delta(h\nu)$ the measured quantum yield corresponding to $1 + g(h\nu)$ is obtained from Eq. (1) and shown in Fig. 4 as a function of the

FIG. 2: Photodiode alignment in wedge trap configuration with light path for 7-reflection PQED.

FIG. 3: Measured responsivity for 7-reflection PQED at p -polarization (black crosses), s -polarization (red dots) from Ref. 20, and ideal responsivity $e/(h\nu)$ of silicon photodetector (solid line).

charge-carrier kinetic energy $E = h\nu - E_g$. Above kinetic energy $E = 1.6 \text{ eV}$, experimental quantum yield starts to get values above 1 reaching 1.3 at 4 eV.

We next compare the measured quantum yield with theoretical results. A straightforward calculation of quantum yield assumes that the charge-carrier density of states can be de-

FIG. 4: Quantum yield measured with p (black crosses) and s (red circles) polarizations. Solid line is calculated by Eq. (3) with $\Delta E = 0$ for $E > 3$ eV (blue) and $\Delta E = 0.25$ eV for $E < 2.3$ eV (green). Blue dotted line represents the transition from $\Delta E = 0$ to $\Delta E = 0.25$ eV.

scribed by that of free carriers, while more detailed derivations consider the energy band structure in silicon lattice.^{1,4,10} According to those calculations, the excess number of electron-hole pairs per absorbed photon as a function of photon energy $h\nu > E_g$ is given by

$$g(h\nu) = \int_0^{h\nu - E_g} P(h\nu, E) N(E) dE, \quad (2)$$

where $P(h\nu, E)$ is the probability distribution of generating a hole or electron of kinetic energy E and $N(E)$ is the average number of electron-hole pairs produced by impact ionization by a carrier with initial energy E above the energy gap E_g . The maximum energy available for a charge carrier is $h\nu - E_g$.

For low energy transfer, $P(h\nu, E)$ can be approximated by a sum of two delta functions of E peaked at zero and at $h\nu - E_g$.¹⁰ As low photon energies are our primary interest here, we use the delta function approximation leading to $g(h\nu) \approx N(h\nu - E_g)$, because $N(0) = 0$. It is then assumed that the charge carrier density of states can be described by that of free carriers which gives^{1,10}

$$g(h\nu) = \left[1 + A_1 (h\nu - E_g - E_{ph} - \Delta E)^{1/2} / (h\nu - 2E_g - \Delta E)^{7/2} \right]^{-1}, \quad (3)$$

where $A_1 = 105A/(2\pi) = 86.9 \text{ eV}^3$ is the constant derived in Ref. 1, $E_{ph} = 0.063 \text{ eV}$ is the energy of optical phonon in

FIG. 5: Experimental quantum yield from Ref. 22 (blue dots) with 9-reflection trap and quantum yield calculated by Eq. (3) (green curve). Internal losses correction¹⁴ from Fig. 1 and reflectance correction for 9-reflection trap structure are applied to data points, uncertainty is given at 1σ level.

silicon²¹ and ΔE is an energy shift, which is nominally zero but can here be used to relax the above assumption on the charge carrier density of states. Wolf et al.⁵ have compared the results in in Ref. 1 with other experiments³ and more realistic band structure calculations⁴. They found out that around the kinetic energy of 2 eV, the results of Refs. 3 and 4 seem to be shifted to lower energies by $\Delta E = 0.25 \text{ eV}$ relative to Ref. 1.

The quantum yield calculated by Eq. (3) is shown by the solid curve in Fig. 4. It is mostly below the measured data revealing increased impact-ionization probabilities at the kinetic energies of 2.25 eV and 3.23 eV on top of a smooth background curve. These peaks correspond to peaks A and C measured by Kolodinski et al.² close to the same energies, and explained to be caused by hot electrons and hot holes, respectively. It should also be noted that in Fig. 4 we do not see peaks B (2.64 eV) and D (3.47 eV).²

The calculated quantum yield with $\Delta E = 0.25 \text{ eV}$ in Fig. 4 is expected to be applicable at charge carrier energies of about 2 eV and below. In Fig. 5, we apply those calculations to the external quantum efficiency data published in Ref. 22, after correcting for estimated reflection and charge-carrier recombination losses. The measured and calculated quantum yield values agree well when taking into account that the simplified calculated result does not include any fitted parameters. Remarkably, both the data and calculated curve indicate quantum yield above 1 at the kinetic energies of 1.6 eV. The extrapolated quantum yield curve reaches 1 at $E = 1.37 \text{ eV}$ corresponding to a photon wavelength of 498 nm.

Previous studies of quantum yield in silicon provide information on experimental results and calculation methods, but

their main interest has been at energies corresponding to incident photons in the ultraviolet and higher energy ranges. We have described here how those results can be applied at short visible wavelengths. This spectral range has recently become important for quantum yield studies because of the need to extend the predicted spectral responsivity of PQED across the full silicon photodetector range. For the results at lowest energies, we show that the threshold kinetic energy of impact ionization is at 1.6 eV or below.

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